

Low Cerebroplacental Ratio as a Predictor of Adverse Perinatal Outcome in Pregnancies Complicated by Fetal Growth Restriction

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Abstract:

Background: Though cerebroplacental ratio (CPR) has shown good role in predicting poor perinatal outcomes in normal pregnancies, its role in FGR (fetal growth restriction) pregnancies remains poorly understood. This study aims to evaluate the predictive value of the CPR in determining adverse perinatal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by FGR.

Methods: A cohort of 100 pregnant women with a gestational age of between 28 and 37 weeks and diagnosed with FGR was assessed and followed up till birth. CPR was calculated using pulsatility index of uterine and middle cerebral artery and a value of <1 was considered low. Perinatal outcomes were recorded, including birth weight, APGAR scores, NICU admissions, fetal distress, and perinatal death. Significance was set at p-value <0.05 .

Results: The mean age of the participants was 28.1 years with 54% being primigravida. Among the pregnancies studied, 47% had a CPR <1 . Mean birth weight was 1.87 ± 0.33 kg. Adverse perinatal outcomes were observed in 15% of cases. CPR <1 was significantly associated with lower birth weight (p-value = 0.02) and adverse perinatal outcomes (p-value = 0.04).

Conclusion: The study highlights the importance of CPR as a predictor of adverse perinatal outcomes in FGR pregnancies. The significant association between low CPR and poor perinatal outcomes emphasizes the need for its integration into routine obstetric practice to improve the management and outcomes of high-risk pregnancies.

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Introduction

Fetal growth restriction (FGR) is a significant complication in pregnancy, associated with increased risks of perinatal morbidity and mortality. It is characterized by a fetus that fails to achieve its genetically predetermined growth potential, often due to placental insufficiency [1]. Perinatal morbidity includes asphyxia, hypoglycaemia, hypothermia, increased neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admissions, stillbirth and impaired neurological and cognitive development later in life. It necessitates vigilant antenatal monitoring and timely interventions to mitigate risks.

Prediction of adverse perinatal outcomes is one of the main purposes of obstetrical practices in pregnancies affected by FGR. Fetal Doppler ultrasound significantly improves surveillance and management, therefore improving perinatal and neonatal outcomes. Among the parameters assessed for fetal well-being, the cerebroplacental ratio

(CPR) has emerged as a promising marker for evaluating fetal compromise and predicting perinatal outcomes. The CPR is calculated as the ratio of middle cerebral artery (MCA) to umbilical artery (UA) pulsatility index (PI) values, measured by Doppler ultrasound [2].

The CPR reflects the balance between fetal cerebral and placental blood flow. A low CPR indicates a redistribution of blood flow towards the brain, a phenomenon known as the "brain-sparing effect," which occurs in response to hypoxia [3]. This adaptive mechanism aims to preserve oxygen delivery to the brain at the expense of other organs. However, a persistently low CPR is associated with adverse perinatal outcomes, including stillbirth, neonatal morbidity, and neurodevelopmental impairments [4]. For instance, a study by Mariam Lotfy Mohamed et al. found that neonates with a CPR ≤ 1.1 had significantly higher rates of cesarean delivery for intrapartum fetal compromise, lower

Apgar scores, and increased NICU admissions [5]. Similarly, the CEPRA study highlighted the utility of CPR in guiding the timing of delivery in pregnancies with reduced fetal movements, showing that a low CPR was associated with a higher risk of adverse neonatal outcomes [6].

This study aims to evaluate the role of low CPR as a predictor of adverse perinatal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by FGR. By systematically assessing the relationship between CPR and perinatal outcomes, this research seeks to enhance the understanding of CPR's prognostic value and support its integration into clinical practice for better management of high-risk pregnancies.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Population: This was a prospective, observational cohort study conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, SMS Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur between April 2019 and March 2020. We recruited 100 singleton pregnant women with a gestational age of between 28 and 37 weeks, who were diagnosed with FGR during routine antenatal care. Cases with multiple pregnancies, congenital/chromosomal fetal abnormalities, and premature rupture of membrane were excluded from the study.

The study protocol was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee of SMS Medical College, Jaipur and all procedures were conducted as per ethical standards and guidelines for human research. Informed consent was obtained from all pregnant women before their participation.

All pregnant women at the antenatal clinic underwent screening with clinical method of measuring fundal height. If it was lagging 4 weeks for their gestational age, two-dimensional ultrasound examination (GE Healthcare) with a 5 MHz curvilinear

probe was performed for further confirmation. The diagnosis of FGR was based on the estimated fetal weight below the 10th percentile for gestational age. We estimated gestational age by date of last menstrual period or by first trimester ultrasound.

Measurements: Enrolled pregnant women then underwent Doppler ultrasound evaluation. We calculated the PI of the UA and MCA from three consecutive waveforms during fetal quiescence using the automated trace of the spectral Doppler waveform. The cerebroplacental ratio (MCA PI/UA PI) was calculated, with a ratio considered abnormal if less than 1.

Patients were followed up till birth. Birth weight and perinatal outcomes were recorded. Perinatal outcomes were considered adverse if any of the following were present: APGAR <7 at 5 min, NICU admission, fetal distress and perinatal death.

Statistical analysis:

Statistical analysis was performed with the Stata v12.0. The categorical data was presented as numbers (frequency) and quantitative data was presented as mean and standard deviation. For association with CPR, Student's t-test and Pearson's correlation was used for categorical and continuous data respectively.

Results

Mean age of the women was 28.1 years with majority of them belonging to middle class (47%) and primigravida (54%) (Table 1). 47% of these pregnancies have CPR<1. In terms of perinatal outcome, 13% had very low birth weight i.e., ≤ 1.5 kg. Adverse perinatal outcome as defined earlier was seen in 15% of the cases. Association analysis found that CPR <1 was associated with lower birth weight (p-value - 0.02) and adverse perinatal outcomes (p-value - 0.04) (Table 2).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study population

Variable	n (%)
Age (Mean \pm SD)	28.1 \pm 0.8 years
Socio-economic status	
Lower class	3 (3.0%)
Lower middle class	40 (40.0%)
Middle class	47 (47.0%)
Upper middle class	10 (10.0%)
Parity	
Primigravida	54 (54.0%)
Multigravida	48 (48.0%)
Cerebroplacental ratio (CPR)	
<1	53 (53.0%)
>1	47 (47.0%)
Birth weight (Mean \pm SD)	
0-1.0	6 (6.0%)
1.1-1.5	7 (7.0%)
1.6-2.0	57 (57.0%)

2.1-2.5	30 (30.0%)
Perinatal outcome	
Good outcome	85 (85.0%)
Adverse outcome	15 (15.0%)

*Adverse perinatal outcome defined as the presence of any one of the following: APGAR <7 at 5 min, NICU admission, fetal distress and perinatal death

Table 2: Association of Cerebroplacental Ratio (CPR) with perinatal outcomes

	CPR <1	CPR >1	p-value
Birth weight (Mean ± SD)	1.73 ± 0.39	2.02 ± 0.23	0.02
Perinatal outcomes			
Good outcome	40 (75.47%)	45 (95.74%)	0.04
Adverse outcome	13 (24.53%)	2 (4.26%)	

Discussion

The present study aimed to evaluate the predictive value of the cerebroplacental ratio (CPR) in determining adverse perinatal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by fetal growth restriction (FGR). Our findings underscore the clinical significance of CPR as a marker for fetal well-being and its potential utility in guiding obstetric management.

Notably, 47% of the pregnancies had a CPR <1, indicating a significant proportion of fetuses experiencing compromised blood flow. This finding aligns with previous studies that have identified low CPR as a common feature in FGR pregnancies [7,8].

Our association analysis revealed that a CPR <1 was significantly associated with lower birth weight and adverse perinatal outcomes. These results corroborate the findings of previous research, which has demonstrated that low CPR is a reliable predictor of adverse outcomes in FGR pregnancies [9,10]. Bahado-Singh et al. measured CPR in 203 fetus at risk of IUGR and found that low CPR to be significantly associated with poor perinatal outcomes including high mortality. However, CPR did not appear to correlate significantly with outcome in fetuses at >34 weeks [10]. A systematic review and meta-analysis of 22 studies also reported that CPR is a useful tool in predicting perinatal death in pregnancies with suspected FGR [9].

Despite its clinical significance, the use of CPR in routine obstetric practice remains underutilized. This may be due to variability in the measurement techniques and the lack of standardized thresholds for defining abnormal CPR [11]. Moreover, the interpretation of CPR values can be influenced by gestational age and other maternal-fetal factors, necessitating a comprehensive approach to its application in clinical settings [12]. Standardizing the measurement and interpretation of CPR could enhance its utility as a diagnostic tool and improve perinatal outcomes in high-risk pregnancies.

The strengths of our study include a well-defined cohort and the use of standardized criteria for assessing perinatal outcomes. However, there are limitations that should be acknowledged. The relatively small sample size may limit the generalizability of our findings. Additionally, the observational nature of the study precludes the establishment of causality. Future research with larger, multicentric cohorts and randomized controlled trials is needed to validate our findings and further elucidate the role of CPR in the management of FGR pregnancies.

In conclusion, our study reinforces the importance of CPR as a predictor of adverse perinatal outcomes in pregnancies complicated by FGR. The significant association between low CPR and poor perinatal outcomes highlights the need for its integration into routine obstetric practice. By identifying fetuses at risk, timely interventions can be implemented to improve perinatal outcomes and reduce the burden of FGR-related complications.

References

1. Melamed N, Baschat A, Yinon Y, et al. FIGO (International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics) initiative on fetal growth: Best practice advice for screening, diagnosis, and management of fetal growth restriction. *Int J Gynecol Obstet.* 2021;152(S1):3-57. doi:10.1002/ijgo.13522
2. Moreta D, Benzie R. Cerebro-placental ratio – Is it time to start putting it to use? *Australas J Ultrasound Med.* 2017;20(4):139-140. doi:10.1002/ajum.12077
3. Graupner O, Meister M, Lecker L, et al. Role of the cerebro-placental-uterine ratio in predicting adverse perinatal outcome in low-risk pregnancies at term. *Arch Gynecol Obstet.* 2023; 308(3):849-855. doi:10.1007/s00404-022-06733-8
4. Melekoglu R, Yilmaz E, Yasar S, Hatipoglu I, Kahveci B, Sucu M. The ability of various cerebroplacental ratio thresholds to predict adverse neonatal outcomes in term fetuses exhibiting late-onset fetal growth restriction. *J Peri-*

- nat Med. 2021;49(2):209-215. doi:10.1515/jpm-2020-0244
5. Mohamed ML, Mohamed SA, Elshahat AM. Cerebroplacental ratio for prediction of adverse intrapartum and neonatal outcomes in a term uncomplicated pregnancy. Middle East Fertil Soc J. 2021;26(1):45. doi:10.1186/s43043-021-00090-3
 6. Damhuis SE, Ganzevoort W, Duijnhoven RG, et al. The Cerebro Placental Ratio as indicator for delivery following perception of reduced fetal movements, protocol for an international cluster randomised clinical trial; the CEPRA study. BMC Pregnancy Childbirth. 2021;21(1):285. doi:10.1186/s12884-021-03760-2
 7. Zheng J jie, Zhao H rong, Mao M hong, et al. Comparison and Analysis of Cerebroplacental Ratio and Umbilicocerebral Ratio in the Prenatal Diagnosis and Severity Assessment of Fetal Growth Restriction: A Retrospective Study and Systematic Review. Arch Obstet Gynaecol. 2024;Volume 5(Issue 1):33-39. doi:10.33696/Gynaecology.5.060
 8. Shmueli A, Mor L, Blickstein O, et al. Placental pathology in pregnancies with late fetal growth restriction and abnormal cerebroplacental ratio. Placenta. 2023;138:83-87. doi:10.1016/j.placenta.2023.05.010
 9. Conde-Agudelo A, Villar J, Kennedy SH, Papageorghiou AT. Predictive accuracy of cerebroplacental ratio for adverse perinatal and neurodevelopmental outcomes in suspected fetal growth restriction: systematic review and meta-analysis. Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol. 2018;52(4):430-441. doi:10.1002/uog.19117
 10. Bahado-Singh RO, Kovanci E, Jeffres A, et al. The Doppler cerebroplacental ratio and perinatal outcome in intrauterine growth restriction. Am J Obstet Gynecol. 1999;180(3):750-756. doi:10.1016/S0002-9378(99)70283-8
 11. Baschat AA, Gembruch U. The cerebroplacental Doppler ratio revisited. Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol. 2003;21(2):124-127. doi:10.1002/uog.20
 12. Bhide A, Badade A, Khatal K. Assessment of reproducibility and repeatability of cerebroplacental ratio. Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol. 2019;235:106-109. doi:10.1016/j.ejogrb.2018.12.027